

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH TERVALENT METALS. PART X. HYDROXO-AQUO COBALDIC BISBIGUANIDINE AND ITS SALTS.

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Diaminocobaltic bisbiguanide complex has been prepared from the oxidation of cobaltous biguanide in presence of ammonia. The removal of ammonia from the latter with consequent hydrolysis in aqueous solution has led to the production of hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanide complex, resembling the corresponding chromium derivative. A series of salts, *viz.* sulphate, chloride, nitrate, dithionate, sulphite and thiosulphate, have been prepared, besides the free hydrated base. The last named, on dehydration, gave rise to a diol-dicobalt-tetrakisbiguanidine. The violet thiosulphate, on treatment with water or with an excess of sodium thiosulphate, gave a green, insoluble product which proved to be a μ -thiosulphato-tetrakisbiguanide dithiosulphato-dicobalt. The complex hydroxo-aquo sulphate gave on dehydration a sulphato-hydroxo-cobaltic bisbiguanide with elimination of the aquo-group from the complex by the sulphato radical.

In a previous communication of the series (Rây and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 621) an account of the cobaltic trisbiguanidine and its various salts, which closely resemble the corresponding chromium compounds (Rây and Saha, *ibid.*, 1937, 14, 670), was given. Hence, the preparation of chromium bisbiguanidine and its salts (Rây and Saha, *ibid.*, 1938, 15, 353, 633) at once suggested the possibility of formation of similar cobalt complexes, a description of which is given in the present paper.

Chromium trisbiguanidine salts were found to hydrolyse slowly in aqueous solution into hydroxo-aquo-bisbiguanidine derivatives with elimination of a molecule of biguanide (Rây and Saha, *loc. cit.*). Cobaltic trisbiguanidine compounds on the other hand are quite stable and remain perfectly unaltered in aqueous solution either on keeping for a long time or when heated. The preparation of cobaltic bisbiguanidine compounds—the hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidine derivatives—can, however, be directly made from the cobaltous bisbiguanidine hydrate by oxidising the latter with air in presence of strong ammonia, a red diaminocobaltic bisbiguanide derivative being produced as an intermediate product. The latter, on further treatment with air in aqueous solution, loses ammonia giving rise to a violet liquid, which, on neutralisation with

sulphuric acid and keeping in the cold, yields red-violet crystals of the sulphate.

where $\text{BigH} = \text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_7$, one molecule of biguanide.

These hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic complexes are very similar to the corresponding chromium compounds in all respects, but much more stable than the latter.

The hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium hydroxide hydrate, $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2.\text{OH}.\text{H}_2\text{O}](\text{OH})_2.\text{H}_2\text{O}$, when heated to 80° , loses water even from the complex zone (total loss of water = 20.78%), giving rise to a dark brown product of the composition $\text{Co}(\text{Big})_2\text{OH}$, which can be represented by the only constitution,

(A diol-tetrakisbiguanidine dicobalt)

This is supported by the fact that on exposure to air the diol compound regains only 7.8% of its own weight of water without any change of its colour. An evidence in favour of the *cis*-configuration of the hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanide compounds is derived from this.

The violet hydroxo-aquo-sulphate, when heated to 80° , lost not only its 2.5 molecules of water of crystallisation but also the water molecule from inside the complex zone, giving rise to a brownish violet acido-hydroxo derivative—a behaviour analogous to that of the chloride of the chromium series (Ray and Saha, *loc. cit.*). No diol derivative was, however, formed in this case, because the dried product regained its violet colour and almost all its original water.

The chloride, $[\text{OH}.\text{H}_2\text{O}.\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{Cl}_2.\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which crystallises with one molecule of water, loses its crystal water at 90° and more at higher temperature leading to the partial formation of a chloro-hydroxo derivative, $[\text{OH}.\text{Cl}.\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{Cl}$.

The preparation of hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium thiosulphate has revealed an interesting phenomenon. By the action of a solution of sodium thiosulphate on that of the complex chloride in equivalent amount in the cold, violet crystals of the hydroxo-aquo-thiosulphate were readily precipitated. If, however, an excess of thiosulphate solution be added, or if the violet crystals be left in contact with the solution for some time, specially in the presence of a trace of dilute acetic or other acids, an almost insoluble green product of the composition, $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_2 (\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, is obtained. At 90° this loses its water molecules without any change of colour. None of the thiosulphate groups could be removed by treatment with barium chloride solution in the cold. The substance reacted neutral to litmus. On boiling with water it decomposed giving an orange solution (alkaline reaction) and a dull green residue. From the orange solution crystals of cobaltic trisbiguanidinium thiosulphate separated out on cooling. After filtering off the latter, the solution was found to contain biguanide and $\text{S}_4\text{O}_6^{2-}$ (tetrathionate) besides $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ (thiosulphate). The dull green residue, on analysis, proved to be a basic cobaltous thiosulphate. From a consideration of all these facts the following constitution

might be assigned to the above described green product, one of the thiosulphate groups acting as a bridge between the two cobalt atoms. The alternative formula, $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{OH}_2 \cdot \text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_2 \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ is barred by the fact that the water molecule is lost below 90° and hence is unlikely to be present inside the complex zone. Moreover, no ionisable thiosulphate radical could be detected by treatment with barium chloride solution, though silver nitrate and lead acetate removed all the thiosulphate from the substance. A third possible structure, $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]_2 \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, is also untenable for the reasons already stated. Besides, it is a well established fact that the thiosulphate radical usually occupies only one co-ordination position. The decomposition of the green product by boiling with water is rather complicated and can be represented more or less as follows.

It was observed that when the violet hydroxo-aquo-thiosulphate changes to the green product in contact with water, the latter turns strongly alkaline. This is obviously due to the formation of some free hydroxo-aquo base as represented in the following scheme.

The formation of the green product from the violet hydroxo-aquo salt, as already stated, is accelerated by the addition of a trace of acetic acid. On the other hand, it has been found that the reverse change occurs by the addition of dilute alkali to the green substance. The behaviour of the violet and the green product and their mutual conversion are summarised below.

Besides the compounds described above, nitrate, sulphate and dithionate of the complex cobaltic bisbiguanide have been prepared.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Diaminocobaltic bisBiguanidinium Sulphate.—Cobaltous bisbiguanidine, prepared by the action of strongly alkaline (with NaOH) biguanide sulphate solution in calculated quantity upon a solution of cobalt chloride, was washed free of alkali by decantation as rapidly as possible to avoid oxidation by air. The product was filtered, treated with concentrated ammonia and the mixture was oxidised by passing a brisk current of air through it for several hours, fresh ammonia being added from time to time. The silky yellow crystalline biguanidine gradually dissolved to form a red

solution leaving a little brownish black residue. This was filtered off. The filtrate often deposited red crystals on cooling. The liquid was then neutralised with dilute sulphuric acid and kept in the cold for a day or two, when red crystals of diamino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium sulphate separated out from the solution. These were purified by recrystallisation from dilute ammonia. The purified product was first washed with cold water containing a little ammonia, then with alcohol and afterwards dried in air. The substance dissolves in cold water forming a red solution which, on slight warming, readily turns violet due to the formation of hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidiniumsulphate by hydrolysis. {Found: N, 30·60; Co, 10·84; SO₄, 26·46. [(NH₂)₂.Co.(BigH⁺)₂]₂(SO₄)₁.12H₂O requires N, 30·71; Co, 10·78; SO₄, 26·34 per cent}.

Hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Sulphate.—The red solution, formed from cobaltous biguanidine and ammonia during the preparation of the previous compound, on further treatment with air current for a long time, gradually turned violet with separation of some brownish black precipitate. When the colour of the liquid became quite deep violet, or when violet crystals appeared on the walls of the vessel, it was filtered. The filtrate was then neutralised with dilute H₂SO₄ and kept in the cold for crystallisation when beautiful, needle-shaped, violet crystals separated in quantities on the walls of the basin in a day or two. These were admixed with a small amount of orange-coloured crystals of cobaltic trisbiguanidium sulphate. These latter were removed by digesting the product several times with hot water in a mortar. The purified violet crystals were then filtered, washed first with cold water, then with alcohol and finally dried over CaCl₂.

The substance forms long rectangular violet prisms, sparingly soluble in hot water. It is decomposed by mineral acids. {Found: N, 31·80; Co, 13·53; SO₄, 22·14. [OH.H₂O Co(BigH⁺)₂]SO₄.2·5H₂O requires N, 32·03; Co, 13·50; SO₄, 21·97 per cent}.

When heated to 80°, the substance lost 14·4% of water (3·5H₂O) and corresponded to the composition, [OH.SO₄.Co(BigH⁺)₂], a sulphato-hydroxo-bisbiguanidinium cobalt. The colour changed to brownish violet. On exposure to air at the ordinary temperature the product regained its original violet colour with absorption of 14·2% of its own weight of water (3 mols), corresponding to a dihydrated hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium sulphate.

Hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Chloride.—The complex sulphate was digested with a cold concentrated solution of the calculated quantity of barium chloride in a mortar till the decomposition was complete.

From the filtrate from barium sulphate, the complex chloride was precipitated by the addition of absolute alcohol. The crystals of the chloride were dissolved in water and purified by reprecipitation with alcohol. The substance forms violet, rectangular prisms like the sulphate. {Found : N, 35'88 ; Cl, 18'60 ; Co, 15'44. $[\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{Cl}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 36'36 ; Cl, 18'44 ; Co, 15'31 ; per cent}.

Equivalent conductivity at 26°.

v (dilution in litres)	32	64	128	256	512	1024
λ_v ...	93'76	100'96	107'90	110'41	114'12	121'16
λ_v (mean) ...	120'6					

$\lambda_m = \lambda_v(1 + n_1 \times n_2 \cdot 0'692 \cdot v^{-\frac{1}{2}})$, where n_1 and n_2 are the valences of the cation and the anion (*cf.* Walden, "Leitvermögen der Lösungen," 1925, V, p. 33).

The equivalent mobility of $[\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]^{++} = 120'6 - 76'54 = 44'06$, the ionic mobility of chlorine being 76'54 at 26°. The value is somewhat lower than that of the corresponding complex chromium ion, λ_{1024} for which is 136'1 mhos at 28 3° (Rây and Saha, *loc. cit.*).

At 85° the substance loses 4'2% of water, which corresponds to its water of hydration ($\text{H}_2\text{O} = 4'7\%$). Further loss occurred above 90° and the substance decomposed at 120° with loss of 8'9% of water.

The violet solution of the chloride, when heated to boiling, turns brown with slight decomposition.

Hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Hydroxide and Diol-tetrakisBiguanidine Dicobalt.—The dark violet, needle-shaped crystals of the base were precipitated by the addition of cold caustic soda solution to that of the complex chloride. These were washed first with ice-cold water, then with alcohol and finally dried in CO_2 -free air. [Found : N, 40'02 ; Co, 16'86. $[\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2](\text{OH})_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 40'20 ; Co, 16'95 per cent}.

When heated to 80° the substance loses 20'78% of water forming a dark brownish violet product—the diol-tetrakisbiguanidine dicobalt (Calc. H_2O , 20'70%). On exposure to air at the room temperature the diol compound absorbed 7'8% of its own weight of water forming a partial hydroxide.

The aqueous solution of the base, when heated to boiling, decomposes with separation of a brown precipitate.

Hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium nitrate was prepared by neutralising an aqueous solution of the above described base with dilute nitric acid and precipitating the complex nitrate from the solution by alcohol.

The violet crystals were washed first with ice-cold water, then with alcohol and afterwards dried in air. {Found: Co, 14'10; NO₂, 29'85. [OH.H₂O.Co(BigH⁺)₂](NO₂)₂ requires Co, 14'03; NO₂, 29'52 per cent}.

Hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Sulphite.—Blue crystals of the sulphite were precipitated by the addition of a cold, freshly prepared solution (neutral) of sodium sulphite to the cold mother-liquor left after the separation of the complex sulphate. The crystals were washed with cold water and alcohol. They were then dried over CaCl₂. {Found: Co, 15'70; SO₂, 21'85. [OH.H₂O.Co(BigH⁺)₂]SO₂ requires Co, 15'68; SO₂, 21'28 per cent}.

Hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Dithionate.—Deep violet crystals of the dithionate were precipitated by the addition of a strong solution of sodium dithionate to that of the complex chloride. These were purified by recrystallisation from warm water. {Found: Co, 12'48; S₂O₆, 33'95. [HO.H₂O.Co(BigH⁺)₂]S₂O₆.H₂O requires Co, 12'44; S₂O₆, 33'76 per cent}.

When heated to 105° it lost its water of hydration (Found: H₂O, 3'8%. Calc. H₂O, 3'79 per cent). No more loss occurred when the substance was further heated up to 130°.

Hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisBiguanidinium Thiosulphate.—Needle-shaped, violet crystals of the thiosulphate were precipitated by mixing solutions of the equivalent amounts of the complex chloride and sodium thiosulphate in the cold. The crystals were immediately filtered, washed first with ice-cold water and then with alcohol. These were dried in air. {Found: Co, 13'75; S₂O₃, 26'42. [OH.H₂O.Co(BigH⁺)₂]S₂O₃.H₂O requires Co, 13'81; S₂O₃, 26'30 per cent}. The substance turns green on shaking with water and the supernatant solution becomes violet-red with alkaline reaction.

Thiosulphato-tetrakisbiguanidinium Dithiosulphato-dicobalt.—When, however, a solution of an excess of sodium thiosulphate was added to that of the complex chloride, the violet thiosulphate, first formed, changed immediately into a bright green insoluble product. The same substance was also obtained by the addition of an excess of sodium thiosulphate to the mother-liquor after the separation of the complex sulphate. The pure violet thiosulphate also changes into the green product on shaking with water and more readily by the addition of a trace of acid. {Found: N, 31'48;

Co, 13'14; S₂O₃, 37'80. $\left[\begin{array}{ccc} \text{S}_2\text{O}_3 & & \text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \\ | & \text{Co-S}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Co} & | \\ (\text{BigH}^+)_2 & & (\text{BigH}^+)_2 \end{array} \right] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 31'32; Co, 13'18; S₂O₃, 37'58 per cent}.

At 90° it lost 4.03 per cent of water. The dried substance gave (Co, 13.80. Calc. : Co, 13.74 ; H₂O, 4.03 per cent). There was no change of colour on dehydration.

The substance is almost insoluble in water. When digested in the cold with barium chloride solution there was no reaction. On boiling with water it decomposed as described before (*vide supra*). When treated with a solution of silver nitrate or lead nitrate all the thiosulphate were removed with formation of a cobaltic *trisbiguanide* salt in solution, which reacted acid. In the case of silver nitrate, black silver sulphide was formed from the decomposition of silver thiosulphate first produced.

By the action of sodium nitrite solution on a solution of the complex chloride a moderately soluble, brick-red precipitate was obtained. It was alkaline in reaction. An orange-yellow precipitate, neutral in character, was obtained by adding a solution of sodium nitrite to the mother-liquor left after the separation of the complex sulphate. By digesting the complex sulphate with a solution of barium nitrite a third compound, orange-red in colour and soluble in hot water, was isolated. All these substances were found to contain NO₂ groups, but none of them could be made sufficiently pure to give definite composition.

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